

**NATURAL &
SEMI-NATURAL
LAND USE
FACTSHEET**

MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES AND PARTICULARITIES NATURAL & SEMI-NATURAL LAND USE

EU MISSION 'A SOIL DEAL FOR EUROPE'

Healthy soils are essential to life on Earth. They are the foundation of our food systems, they also provide clean water and habitats for biodiversity while contributing to climate resilience. Yet, between 60% and 70% of soils in the EU are considered unhealthy. While it can take hundreds of years to form just one centimetre of soil, it can be lost in a single rainstorm or through industrial damage.

The EC launched the Mission '**A Soil Deal for Europe**' - Horizon Europe programme -**to create 100 living labs and lighthouses** in rural and urban areas to drive the transition to healthy soils by 2030.

Funded by the European Union

THE MISSION SOIL WILL¹:

- > Create knowledge and solutions for soil health,
- > Advance the development of a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe,
- > Increase people's awareness of the vital importance of soils,
- > Support the EU's ambition to lead on global commitments, notably the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and contribute to the European Green Deal targets.*

¹ European Commission

[*more information in the Mission implementation plan.](#)

THE 8 MISSION OBJECTIVES

1

Reduce desertification

2

Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

3

Stop soil sealing & increase re-use of urban soils

4

Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration

5

Prevent erosion

6

Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity

7

Reduce the EU global footprint on soils

8

Improve soil literacy in society

THE MISSION SOIL LIVING LABS ARE...

"user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists, and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring, and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption." Factsheet - EU Mission Soil Deal for Europe: Living labs and lighthouses.

CHALLENGES IN NATURAL & SEMI-NATURAL LAND USE

Soils in areas under natural & semi-natural land-use represent the main reservoir of soil carbon and biodiversity. Conservation and restoration of those soils strongly depend on the type of natural habitat to be managed (grassland, forest, etc.) and the extent of the interventions that are required to achieve the desired effects.

The main challenges that SHLLs face in natural & semi-natural land-use soils are:

1. Increasing pollution from air and water causing the disruption of soil functions, e.g., nutrient mineralisation, leading to habitat degradation;
2. Establishment of invasive plant species favoured by soil degradation and changing climatic conditions;
3. Lack of awareness regarding the value of natural soils as low-renewable resources involved in the delivery of important ecosystem services in largely unmanaged areas.

THE QUADRUPLE HELIX TYPES OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN LIVING LABS

An essential feature of Living Labs is their **user-centric approach**, involving all key actors and end-users throughout the innovation process. While specific participants vary by context, they can be grouped using the **Quadruple Helix Model**—Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil Society—forming a **Public-Private-People Partnership (PPPP)** that enables real co-creation and impact.

This inclusive model supports co-learning and ensures that solutions are not only scientifically sound but also practical, economically viable, socially accepted, and environmentally sustainable.

SOME EXAMPLES OF STAKEHOLDERS OF LIVING LABS FOCUSED ON NATURAL & SEMI-NATURAL LAND USE MAY INCLUDE:

- **GOVERNMENT & PUBLIC SECTOR:** Local, regional and national administrations, environmental protection offices, health authorities, natural parks and environmental managers might benefit from Living Labs dealing with conservation, restoration and planning of natural & semi-natural land-use areas of naturalistic value.
- **PRIVATE SECTOR:** Landowners, environmental consultants, landscape managers and farmers can benefit from healthy soils supporting natural vegetation and associated beneficial organisms with positive effects on nearby agricultural lands and urban green areas.
- **ACADEMIA AND RESEARCH:** Universities, research centres and knowledge transfer offices might benefit from the activities of natural & semi-natural land-use Living Labs that support healthy and biodiverse soils in managed areas, offering opportunities to study natural soil functions.
- **CITIZENS, CIVIL SOCIETY & USERS:** citizen organisations, environmental organisations and ordinary citizens might become users of Living Labs focused on the sustainable management and monitoring of natural & semi-natural land-use areas with an added value as healthy spaces for leisure and social activities.

WHICH ADDED VALUE CAN CO-CREATION BRING IN THIS FIELD?

Participation of the main stakeholders on the co-creation of natural & semi-natural land-use Living Labs can lead to monitoring and management solutions that optimise the creation and conservation of natural & semi-natural land-use areas containing different types of healthy soils.

Collaboration between the public and private sectors in the exploitation of the different resources provided by those soils can reduce management costs allowing the creation and/or restoration or further natural areas.

The involvement of ordinary citizens and social organisations in the use and monitoring of natural soils can raise the awareness of the public community about the importance of those soils for the existence of natural areas with significant educational, recreational, aesthetical, and health value.

WHICH ACTIVITIES CAN A NATURAL & SEMI-NATURAL MISSION SOIL LIVING LAB PERFORM?

Promote the participation of the public community in the management of land areas used as a natural green infrastructure around and between villages and cities.

Rise awareness about the overlooked importance of soils in natural & semi-natural land-use areas as strategic reservoirs of useful biodiversity and effective support of natural vegetation of ecological and aesthetic value.

Develop methods to assess the beneficial impact of self-regulated areas with natural vegetation on soils and soil health as subjected to different types of environmental stress.

To be a successful farmer [and soil manager], one must first know the nature of the soil"

**XENOPHON OF ATHENS
OECONOMICUS
C. 400 B.C.**

CRITERIA TO IDENTIFY

LIVING LABS*

Aims

- **Innovation, co-creation**, formal learning
- Contribution to **societal challenges**
- **Improving soil health and related ecosystem services** (= > mission objectives)

Participants

Public-private people partnership:

- **Real soil managers** (farmers, advisors, foresters, city greens managers, allotment holders, etc.) to be at the centre of the innovation process.
- **Other stakeholders:** Associations and organisations with interest in soil health, local or regional government, scientists from a variety of fields outside of soil (natural sciences, social and behavioural sciences), and the wider public.

Activities

- **Co-creation, co-development & experimentation** of innovations improving soil health and related ecosystems
- **Research on impact of these innovative practices on ecosystems**
- **Networking** and **knowledge exchange**
- **Demonstration** (in particular lighthouses)

Context

- Multiple **disciplines** (-> transdisciplinary, inc. social sciences), **methods, dimensions** (technical, economic, social)
- **Place-based** approach and **real-life context** = real farms/forest/urban sites
- **Robust scientific setup** for **ecosystem assessment**
- **Openness**, communication, dissemination

*adapted from McPhee et al. (2021)

LIGHTHOUSES

As lighthouses are sites achieving exemplary performance in terms of soil health improvement, the criteria for selecting them will be based on the **mission objectives**, indicators, and thresholds as defined by the monitoring programme:

- **Demonstration, dissemination, and promotion** to soil managers, the public, and the policy arena, at the landscape scale and beyond, of land-use systems that satisfy criteria for sustainable development, in particular in terms of soil health and related ecosystem services.
- Reaching out to the **policy arena** linking results of the Lighthouses to environmental rules and regulations. This is in line with science-based policy support and governance.

HOW TO PARTICIPATE? TWO LIVING LAB TOPICS

1) Brownfield

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01: Living Labs for soil remediation and green redevelopment of **brownfields**

- **Single-stage** submission
- **Deadline:** 30 September 2025
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - should be located in at least three different Member States and/or Associated Countries

2) Biogeographical regions

HORIZON-MISS-2025-05-SOIL-01-two-stage: Living labs to enhance soil health in **Continental, Boreal and Alpine biogeographical regions**

- **Two-stage** submission (First, applicants submit a brief outline. Selected proposals are then invited to submit a full application)
- **Deadline:** 4 September 2025 (first stage) and 18 February 2026 (second stage).
- 4-5 Living Labs for each application - **Most of the living labs** (i.e., 3 out of 4, or 4 out of 5) must be located **within the chosen region**

Research and Innovation Actions:

100% funding for any actor
Proposals must apply the multi-actor approach
Support to third parties is allowed

WANT TO EXPLORE FURTHER?

Biogeographical Regions factsheet

Both Living Lab topics on the SOILL website

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SOILL HUB

A collaborative space dedicated to soil health.

HELPDESK

A wide network of experts ready to provide guidance and answers on many topics.